

Application of Free Electron Molecular Orbital Model: Absorption Spectra of Cyanine Dyes

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The calculations of the wavelength of maximum absorption of a number of cyanine dyes of different chain lengths by the Free Electron Molecular Orbital technique is reported here. It is demonstrated that a judicious choice of not only the adjustable parameter, L (box length), but also the appropriate chromophoric chain is necessary for a more accurate prediction of the wavelength of maximum absorption. The oscillator strengths of some of these dyes are also reported.

ORGANIC dye stuffs, particularly the polymethine dyes, constituted the most familiar systems for illustration of the applicability of the Free Electron Molecular Orbital (FEMO) model during the initial phases of the development of the model^{1,2}. In most of these applications, the length, L , of the potential box has been more or less regarded as an adjustable parameter. We report here the calculations of the wavelength of maximum absorption of a number of cyanine dyes by the application of the free electron model. The oscillator strengths of some of the dyes are also reported. A general principle for choosing the box length is suggested. It is our desire to demonstrate that in addition to L , which is the adjustable parameter, a proper choice of the chromophoric chain for obtaining the number of π -electrons and hence the quantum states involved in the transition, is also another important criterion.

It is quite well known that, for a system containing M number of π -electrons, the first transition occurs due to the excitation of an electron from $(M/2)$ -th to $(M/2+1)$ -th quantum state and the wavelength, of the maximum absorption is given by

$$\lambda_{max} = \frac{8m_e L^2 c}{h(M+1)} \quad \dots (1)$$

and the oscillator strength, f , by

$$f_{mn} = 1.62 \frac{m^2 n^2}{(n^2 - m^2)^3} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $m = M/2$, $n = (M/2) + 1$,

h = Planck's constant,

m_e = mass of an electron,

c = velocity of light, and

L = length of the one-dimensional box.

I. Calculation of λ_{max}

1. Sulfur, because of its ability to utilise its d -orbitals for participating in the formulation of the

basic chromophoric set, acts as a resonance transmitter and can be treated as a vinyl group³. In dealing with the sulfur containing dyes, we have justifiably assumed the inclusion of sulfur in the basic chromophoric set for the purpose of calculation of the wavelength of maximum absorption.

2. The chromophoric chain of the dyes derived from quinoline-2, can be represented as either of the following two :

the number of π -electrons being 6 for IIa and 10 for IIb. For our computation, we have therefore taken the number of π -electrons as the average of the two, i.e., 8.

TABLE 1—ABSORPTION MAXIMA OF SYMMETRICAL CYANINES

Nature of B	x	L(A°)	M	λ _{max} (nm)	
				Calc.	Obs.
4-Phenyl thiazole	0	(7+2) × 1.39 = 12.51	10	468.2	460
	1	(9+2) × 1.39 = 15.29	12	593.5	560
	2	(11+2) × 1.39 = 18.09	14	718.7	660
Benzothiazole	0	(7+2) × 1.39 = 12.51	10	468.2	460
	1	(9+2) × 1.39 = 15.29	12	593.5	560
	2	(11+2) × 1.39 = 18.09	14	718.7	660
Benzoxazole	1	(6+2) × 1.39 = 11.12	8	453	480
	2	(8+2) × 1.39 = 13.9	10	578	580
	3	(10+2) × 1.39 = 16.68	12	705	680
Quinoline-2	1	$\left[\left(\frac{6+10}{2} \right) + 2 \right] \times 1.9 = 13.9$	10	579	610
	2	$\left[\left(\frac{8+12}{2} \right) + 2 \right] \times 1.39 = 16.68$	12	704	710
Quinoline-4	1	(10+2) × 1.39 = 16.68	12	705	710
	2	(12+2) × 1.39 = 19.46	14	831	820

3. The free electron path is assumed to terminate one bond length beyond the end atoms in accordance with the suggestions of Ruedenberg and Scherr⁴, so that the length of the box is taken as equal to (a+2)l, where a is the number of bonds and l is the average C-C bond length (= 1.39 Å). Table 1 lists the results.

The relatively higher discrepancy in the experimental and calculated values in case of dyes with sulfur containing nuclei is understandable from the fact that inclusion of sulfur in the chromophoric chain produces an asymmetry in the polymethine chain and hence eq. (1) would no more be strictly valid.

II. Oscillator Strength

Evaluation of the oscillator strengths, using Eq. (2) lends support to our postulates made in the calculation of λ_{max}.

The oscillator strength values are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2—OSCILLATOR STRENGTHS OF SYMMETRICAL CYANINES

Nature of B	x	M	Oscillator strength	
			Calc.	Obs.
Benzothiazole	0	10	1.09	1.2 ^a
	1	12	1.30	1.2 ^a
	2	14	1.52	1.6 ^a
Quinoline-2	1	10	1.09	1.3

a) Data from A. L. Sklar; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1942, 10, 524.

Experimental

The dyes were prepared and purified by standard methods reported earlier⁵. The extinction coefficients were measured with a Unicam SP-600 spectrophotometer.

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